

Yoga and Music complement each other

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ABSTRACT:

Music and Yoga complement each other. Yoga is incomplete without music and music is incomplete without yoga. When we do yoga, music creates meditation in it and when we learn or sing music, yoga gives strength to it, so it seems very difficult to separate these two. But in today's run-of-the-mill life, we cannot balance both, so we have to face incompleteness even without wanting to. Today many students start learning music but are unable to complete it. Because, sometimes lack of posture, sometimes lack of concentration, sometimes lack of attention, or any other reason, nowadays the era of shortcuts has come.

Although yoga is a big subject, from the point of music, an attempt has been made to know, learn, and understand, which part of yoga practice is essential. In this article, 1. How can we understand the importance of time and complete the practice of music by doing some effective yoga practice while learning music? Similarly, 2. When we use music while doing yoga, a wonderful result is seen.

KEYWORDS:

Music + Yoga, Mind + Body, Dharna + Sadhana.

Introduction:

Music and Yoga complement each other. Today many students start learning music but are unable to complete it. Because of, sometimes lack of posture, sometimes lack of concentration, sometimes lack of attention, sometimes other things, nowadays the era of shortcuts have come.

Today, we have divided music and yoga practice into two dif-

ferent subjects. Due to this, it has become difficult to balance these subjects. Yoga gives us the knowledge of meditation, concentration, yama, niyama, and asana, whatever is essential for learning it helps to connect it with all kinds of arts and life works. This has been going on since Vedic times, but we just forgot to follow these.

Music is a live magic that requires the blessings of divine power to learn and understand. While using different Naad Sounds and making the balance of prana-vayu, states of consciousness, knowledge, health, salvation, bliss, stability, balance, etc. can be achieved in a human being. By simplifying the same music + yoga practice.

Yoga: Yoga originated in ancient India as a physical, mental, and spiritual practice. First codified by the sage "Patanjali" in his "Yoga Sutras" around 400 C.E., the practice was in fact handed down from teacher to student long before this text arose. Traditionally, this was a one- to-one transmission, but since yoga became popular in the West in the 20th century, group classes have become the norm. The word yoga is derived from the Sanskrit root yuj, meaning "to yoke," or "to unite". The practice aims to create a union between body, mind, and spirit, as well as between the individual self and universal consciousness. Such a union tends to neutralize ego-driven thoughts and behaviors, creating a sense of spiritual awakening.¹

Music - There's music in everything; our bodies, the movement of the planets and stars in the galaxy, the communication between people and animals, as well as the movement of wind and water. In colloquial language, music is considered to be only singing, but in the music world, singing, playing, and dancing in a group of all three is called music, writes Pandit Sharangdev in Sangeet Ratnakar. "Geetam, vadyam tatha nratyem, triyam sangeete muchyathe"²

Music and Yoga - Music and Yoga are very effective ways to reach tranquillity. This is because when you are peaceful and in a peaceful state, you become closer to your spiritual self. Indeed, music and yoga can assist you to attain such a higher level of con-

sciousness. When you work with music and yoga you will combine your mind and body into one. This is why you must find the right music for your yoga session. Your choice of music will set the tone for your entire practice, and it will help you reach that higher level of consciousness, which is what we are all looking for when we decide to do yoga in the first place.

Music and Yoga have an amazing relationship. Music is the best meditation and yoga is the best exercise. When we listen to music, it relaxes and pacifies our mind, body, and soul. In the same way, when we practice yoga, it helps us concentrate and relax the three aspects of ourselves. Both of them are very helpful to each other. Listening to yoga music makes us focus on a single point which is our breathing. It assists us in staying targeted throughout the session and also supports our rest after a tired session workout. Music can help us to relax, concentrate, focus, and even get in the mood to push your body to its limits. While listening to music, try to imagine it as a background for your practice, rather than an object of focus.

There's nothing wrong with listening to music as you do yoga - in fact, there are many psychological benefits. It's just that if your goal is quieting your mind and focusing on your practice, focusing heavily on the music itself will only distract you from that goal. When you do music and yoga at the same time, have them complement each other within you. Music is a great way to set the mood for your yoga session. Today, there is a type of music for every activity and mood. The practice of Yoga can be very beneficial in calming the mind and relieving stress. Music is also a phenomenal tool for stress relief since it calms the nervous system by relaxing the muscles and releasing tension throughout the body. Combining these two things together will make your yoga practice even more enjoyable.³

Nowadays, when we do any work, we use music in it. This keeps the mind engaged in work and the work is done with full focus. Music inspires us to do the work and we finish the work without any stress. It has become a trend to combine music with all activi-

ties. Musical sounds or peaceful sounds are being used with yoga. This increases focus. This keeps the mind more active. In today's scenario, we use music in every activity but we don't have the focus on music practice. Music practice is also a kind of spiritual practice. Music has become only a means of entertainment and useful only for listening. A few people try to understand and practice it. The practice of music is melodious and gives pleasure, but most people are not paying attention to it, music has started appearing as just a useful thing.

Study of music, practice, Naad Sadhana, and the value of the sweetness of music in life, all seem to have become secondary. The relationship of music with the worship of God, attainment of God, joy, spiritual practice, samadhi, etc. through music seems to be inactive. Music practitioners, now find this path difficult. They learn music for fun. It would not be an exaggeration to say that music is the best means of entertainment, but it seems as if the path to samadhi through music has become blurred. To connect music with samadhi or sadhana, we have to connect it with yoga. Yoga is a comprehensive process, but we will discuss only the 8 limbs of the Sadhana Path, which are useful for the practice of music. By following these rules, all knowledge (education or spiritual or the best way to live life) was easily acquired by humans. Because yoga is the balance of our life. This rule was studied in the Gurukul Education System since the Vedic Period.

Those who want to progress in music must study "Yoga Darshan" so that all the problems related to Yoga can be solved. "Patanjali Maharishi" has divided Yoga Philosophy into four parts. 1. Samadhi Pada, 2. Sadhana Pada, 3. Vibhuti Pada, 4. Kaivalya Pada, the main objective of Yoga is to control the tendencies of the mind. Ashtanga yoga means the 8 limbs of sadhana pada. part of Yoga philosophy which has been interpreted by "Maharishi Patanjali" as 8 limbs of Yoga. 1. Yama, 2. Niyama, 3. Asana, 4. Pranayama, 5. Pratyahara, 6. Dharana, 7. Dhyana, 8. Samadhi.

With the combination of yoga and music, the all-round development of a human being can be achieved. The researcher is trying to convey this. Through this, man's veil of ignorance is removed and they acquire self-realized knowledge.

1. Yama - At the beginning of Patanjali's eight-fold path of yoga lays the Yamas: the moral, ethical, and societal guidelines for the practicing yogi. These guidelines are all expressed in the positive, and thus become emphatic descriptions of how a yogi behaves and relates to their world when truly immersed in the unitive state of yoga. It has five subrules
 - 1.1 Ahimsa (non-violence) is the practice of non-violence, which includes physical, mental, and emotional violence towards others and the self.
 - 1.2 Satya (truthfulness) urges us to live and speak our truth at all times. Walking the path of truth is a hard one.
 - 1.3 Asteya (non-stealing) The practice of Asteya entails not committing theft physically and not causing or approving of anyone else doing so—in mind, word, or action.
 - 1.4 Brahmacharya (continence) One of the main goals of yoga is to create and maintain balance. The simplest method for achieving balance is by practicing Brahmacharya, creating moderation in all of our activities.
 - 1.5 Aparigraha (non-coveting) urges us to let go of everything that we do not need, possessing only as much as necessary.

When we practice the Yama we are striving towards living a healthier, holier, and more peaceful life, and at the same time, we strengthen our powers of awareness, will, and discernment. Engaging in these practices is not an easy task, yet by doing so we fortify our character, improve our relationships with others, and further our progress along the path of sangeet sadhana.⁴

2. Niyama - These practices extend the ethical codes of conduct

provided in his first limb, yama to the practicing yogi's internal environment of body, mind, and spirit. The practice of Niyama helps us maintain a positive environment in which to thrive and gives us the self-discipline, humility, and inner strength necessary to progress along the path of yoga and music. It has five subrules –

- 2.1 Shaucha (purification and cleanliness) The yogis discovered that impurities in both our external environment and our internal body adversely affect our state of mind, and prevent the attainment of real wisdom and spiritual liberation.
- 2.2 Santosha (contentment) The yogis tell us that when we are perfectly content with all that life gives us, then we attain true joy and happiness.
- 2.3 Tapas (asceticism and self-discipline) The yogi practice of intense self-discipline and attainment of willpower. Basically, Tapas is doing something you do not want to do that will have a positive effect on your life.
- 2.4 Svadhyaya (self-study and self-reflection) is the ability to see our true divine nature through the contemplation of our life's lessons and through the meditation on the truths revealed by seers and sages.
- 2.5 Ishvara Pranidhana (devotion and self-surrender) is the dedication, devotion, and surrender of the fruits of one's practice to a higher power.

It creates a solid foundation and strong container for the yogi to move into the deeper stages of yoga with focus, inner strength, and success. It is also important for music practice to follow the rules related to music.⁵

3. Asana – Asana are the physical body positions or poses of yoga that form the foundation of modern hatha yoga and music practice. Asana is a Sanskrit word meaning “posture,” “seat,” or “place.” Asana are the physical positions. Many of the asana

names have come from the shapes and movements of animals and elements of the natural world. Yoga postures- padmasan, veerasan, sawasan, sukhasan, and sthir- sukhasan. The sthir-sukhasan can be held comfortably and motionless. Asana is a backborn of music sadhana. A correct posture gives you great results.⁶

4. Pranayam - Pranayama is a collection of breathing exercises developed by ancient yogi for purification, mental focus, and healing. Prana translates into “life force energy,” and Yama translates into “control or mastery of.” Thus, pranayama is a breathing technique used to control, cultivate, and modify the amount, quality, flow, and direction of vital energy in the body. Pranayama is often defined simply as “breath control” and is a primary component in traditional yoga and music practice. The easiest and fastest way to increase the prana in the body is to change our breathing to affect the quality and quantity of air taken into the lungs. When your prana flow or energy channels are blocked or restricted, you may experience a lack of focus and negative emotions like anxiety, fear, worry, tension, depression, anger, and grief. When your prana or energy channels are open and flowing freely and smoothly the mind becomes calm, focused, happy, positive, and enthusiastic.⁷
5. Pratyahara - It is the pivotal point in the practice of music where the path leads from the exterior to the interior landscape of the body. Pratyahara translates directly as “sense withdrawal” With this awareness and focus, we can move deeper into the practice of yoga/music, learning to move through our limitations, fears, and expectations. We have 5 senses (smell, touch, see, taste, and hearing by nose, skin, eye, tongue, and ear). The key to practicing pratyahara is observing the body, breath, and sensations as a detached witness drashta as if you were watching and feeling someone else’s body.⁸
6. Dharana - Dharana is a Sanskrit word, that means concentration

or single focus. “Dha” means “holding, carrying, or maintaining”, and “ana” means “other or something else.” Meditation is an incredibly powerful tool that can be difficult and frustrating to learn. When you start practicing, you discover how easy it is, to be distracted by all the other thoughts and emotions that swirl around in your mind. Dharana is the sustained practice of focused concentration on a single object. you can learn to be focused in the midst of everyday life, you’ll find yourself more productive, relaxed, and able to deal with stress more effectively.⁹

7. Dhyana - Meditation is a powerful tool to calm your mind, reduce stress, and improve your overall well-being, yet it can be mystifying and challenging to get started. But fear not, with the proper guidance and some patience, you can embark on a transformative meditation journey that will enhance your physical, mental, and spiritual health. Meditation is the focusing of the mind on a single object with the goal of creating the cessation of all thought. As thoughts dissipate, the mind becomes quiet, and we are able to be fully in the present moment. The techniques of meditation are simple and easy to learn, but the ability to keep the mind focused takes time, patience, and practice. These stages provide a framework for achieving self-realization and a balanced and fulfilling life. Dhyana practice makes us morally focused in music practice.¹⁰
8. Samadhi - Patanjali defines Samadhi as a state of attention or concentration. Yoga Sutra as a map, the body/mind as your vehicle, and your yoga practices the fuel. Samadhi is the eighth and final step on the path of yoga, as defined by Patanjali’s Yoga Sutras. The term is derived from several Sanskrit roots; “sam” meaning “together” or “completely,” “a” meaning “toward” and “dhi”, meaning “put.” Direct translations vary, and interpretations range from “bliss” to “liberation” and even “enlightenment.”

In Hinduism and Buddhism, samadhi is regarded as the pinnacle of all spiritual and intellectual activity, in addition to being a precondition for attaining samsara (release from the cycle of death and rebirth). In yoga, samadhi is considered to be the state in which individual and universal consciousness unite. Being in music, learning, singing, dedicating to God is the state of Samadhi. ¹¹

Conclusion:

The musician says that music is also a way to reach Samadhi. It is a sweet, melodious, and simple way of bliss and enlightenment. To achieve this, we can use these eight rules of Yoga. These are also applicable in music. Being in music, learning, singing, dedicating, to God is the state of Samadhi.

Endnotes:

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